

ALISHER NAVO'S WORKS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS ON THE LEARNING OF THE LANGUAGE

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Abstract : This article talks about Alisher Navoi's great merits in the formation, development and improvement of the Uzbek literary language, the language and style of the works belonging to the poet's genius, and the scientific research carried out in Turkology and Uzbek linguistics .

Key words: Alisher Navoi, ancient Turkic language, old Turkic language, Turkic (old Uzbek) language, Uzbek literary language, native language, Arabic, Persian -Tajik language, poetic and prose works.

"As we have set ourselves the great goal of establishing the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, we must create the environment and conditions that will educate new Khorezms, Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navoi, and Babur. In this, first of all, development of education and training, establishment of a healthy lifestyle, development of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea .¹

Sh.M. Mirziyoev

The Uzbek national language has passed the stages of formation and development of several hundred years, and currently its history goes back to the period of the ancient Turkic (VII-X) language. The Orhun-Enasoy inscriptions written in Turkic-run script, translated works from Sanskrit, Sogdian, and Chinese

¹<https://www.google.com/search?q=President+Shavkat+Mirziyoyev's+Address+to+the+Supreme+Majlis&aq=chrome.2.69i57j69i59l3j46i67i175i199j69i60j69i61j69i60.9047j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>

languages make it possible to get specific information about the linguistic situation, literary language, and spoken language of the vast area where the ancestors lived during the Turkic khanate .

The direct successor of this language, at the same time, the old Uzbek literary language, formed on the basis of the old Turkic language (XI-XIV), which differs from it with specific and significant changes that occurred in its existing levels, clearly manifested the characteristics of the literary language formed on the basis of the colloquial language of different tribes, is the ancient Turkic language and is the successor of Old Turkic, which incorporates to a certain extent the vocabulary, sound system and grammatical structure (like other related Turkic languages).

It can be said without exaggeration that the Qarluq-Uyghur written language, which was formed in the eastern regions of the Karakhanid kingdom and produced such a masterpiece as "Kutadgu Bilig", had a strong influence on the old Uzbek literary language until the 16th century.

The development of Turkish literature in Central Asia dates back to the 11th-15th centuries. The formation of the old Uzbek literary language, founded by the great poet, thinker and statesman Alisher Navoi, is also closely related to this period ².The language of a particular nation is formed, polished, standardized on the basis of long-lasting historical events. In it to the ancestors special feature , character, priceless bisot known level to the eye thrown away stands.

Tendency to the principles of continuity and continuity is a key characteristic of language, which acts as a kind of bond or, in other words, a bridge, between ancestors and descendants.

Undoubtedly, great people - scholars, poets, writers, thinkers, statesmen,

². Фозилов Э. Ўзбек адабий тилининг шаклланиш тарихи ҳақида // Ўзбек тили тарихи масалалари. - Тошкент: Фан, 1977. -Б.3

scientists - play a significant role in the formation, development and improvement of the native language. The Uzbek literary language, which has its own path of development for several thousand years, is no exception. Today, it takes a worthy place not only among the sister Turkic languages, but also among the developed world languages, thanks to the great service of many writers such as Yusuf Khos Hajib, Mahmud Koshgari, Ahmad Yassavi, Zamakhshari, Nasiruddin Rabguzi, Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Ogahi, Abdulla Qadiri, Oybek. is available.

Without exaggeration, the role of Alisher Navoi, its literal founder, in the formation of the Uzbek literary language and its current state is incomparable.

Poem and prose works belonging to the poet's genius were of a high artistic and ideological-spiritual level, so they spread to other regions at lightning speed and gained the attention of the people of science. As a result his works based on made up row dictionaries and grammar surface came ³

Navoi, who devoted his entire conscious life to the cause of national unity, prosperity and peace of the people and the nation, with his immortal poetry, epics, scientific and artistic works, not only from China to Khurasan, but also from the Kipchak Dashti, Volgaboyi, beyond the Caucasus to Asia Minor and Europe to the decree of his throne", proving in practice that the Turkish (old Uzbek) language is not weak in any way compared to the highly developed, in particular, Arabic and Persian-Tajik languages, but on the contrary, it is superior in some aspects, that it is possible to write wonderful poetic divans and create "Khamsa" in Turkish. gave

The wealth and charm of the Turkic (old Uzbek) language, the wide opportunities inherent in it, are clearly realized in the example of Navoi's work. Linguists are encouraged to study the linguistic features of the literary heritage on

³ Абдурахмонов Ф., Рустамов А. Навоий тилининг грамматик хусусиятлари. –Тошкент: Фан, 1984. -Б.3.

a deep scientific basis. motivated him to come to theoretical conclusions about the levels.

In this direction, many researches were conducted in Turkology and Uzbek linguistics, scientific works, dictionaries, pamphlets, articles were published, conferences were convened. The scope and quantity of studies devoted to language features of Navoi's works do not allow to mention them separately. But A.K. Borovkov, A.N. Kononov, A.M. Shcherbak, G'. Abdurahmonov, A. Rustamov, E. Fozilov, O. Usmonov, B. Bafoev, K. Eraslan, Ya. Ekmann contributed a significant share to Navoi studies. , E. Umarov, B. Hasanov, M. It is appropriate to acknowledge the work of such linguists as Rahmatullaeva, A. Karimov, I. Nosirov, Z. Hamidov, S. Ozonder ⁴.

The language lexicon of Navoi's works is the most studied level in Navoi studies. The lexemes used in the text of the poet's works were determined from the point of view of the statistical method ⁵, their lexical-semantic, stylistic, linguopoetic properties were studied, a series of synonyms and a system of some terms were researched.

As we know, the old Uzbek literary language is a polished, standardized form of the universal national language created by the Uzbek people, and it can be said that persons with high linguistic culture, that is, statesmen, thinkers, philosophers, worked hard on its improvement. In particular, the role of representatives of artistic creativity - poets and writers - in the formation of the old Uzbek literary language and its norms is incomparable.

In conclusion, we can say that in the transformation of the old Uzbek literary language, which is the highest form of the national language and is part of

⁴Эгамова Ш. Алишер Навоий асарлари тилидаги қадимги туркий лексика тадқиқи (структур-грамматик, функционал-семантик аспектларда) : Филол. фан. номз. ...дисс. автореф. – Тошкент, 2007.

⁵ Бафоев Б. Навоий асарлари лексикаси. –Тошкент: Фан, 1983. -157 б.

the national language, into a literal literary language, in its rise to the level of the Arabic and Persian-Tajik languages, which have a high position in the world of the Middle Ages, and the Persian-Tajik languages, wonderful ghazals are also written in it. The incomparable courage, selfless work, patriotism, patriotism of the great Alisher Navoi, as well as the unique talent given to him by the Creator, lie in clearly showing that it is possible to interpret "Khamsa", create scientific works, and conduct philosophical observations.

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